

**THE STRENGTH OF REINFORCING FIBRES:
WEAKEST LINK PRINCIPLE - A NON-PARAMETRIC TEST**
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ABSTRACT

The assumption that the strength of brittle fibres is determined by the strength of their weakest segment is fundamental to the statistical analysis of experimental data. Unfortunately there are many factors which tend to reduce the reliability of this data so that the "weak link" principle is not always obeyed. These factors are discussed and a modified test procedure and analysis described which allows the compliance with weak link theory to be assessed without recourse to Weibull statistics. This procedure has been applied to an extensive set of tensile test data on a high strength carbon fibre.

KEYWORDS: Fibre, Carbon, Strength, Statistical analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

An understanding of the strength of the reinforcing fibres is essential to any analysis of the mechanical properties of a composite material. It is however a very elusive quantity to measure reliably. Most reinforcing fibres, eg carbon, glass and silicon-carbide, are brittle solids and, under tensile loading, are elastic up to the point of failure.

Their strength is considered to be determined by stress-concentrating "flaws" which are distributed over the surface and within the bulk of the material. If a length of such a fibre is subjected to a uniform, monotonically increasing, tensile stress it will fail when the stress at the most severe flaw, contained within the test length, is sufficient to propagate a brittle fracture across the fibre. A fibre may then be considered to consist of a large number of very short segments connected in series. Failure will occur in the segment which

contains the most severe flaw. This is the basis of the weak-link hypothesis which may be expressed statistically by:

$$S_L(\sigma) = \{S_1(\sigma)\}^L \quad (1)$$

where $S_L(\sigma)$ is the probability that a fibre of length L survives a stress σ . It follows that if a random [Poisson] distribution of self-similar flaws of variable intensity is assumed, then a shorter length of fibre will be statistically stronger than a longer length. This may be tested experimentally by performing a large number of tensile tests on samples of the fibre over a range of test gauge lengths.

The resulting test data consists of sets of strengths each measured at one gauge length. These sets may be analyzed according to the Weibull 2-parameter model [equation 2] to generate a *characteristic stress* [or *scaling parameter*] σ_0 , and a *Weibull modulus* [or *shape parameter*], w , for each set.

$$S_L(\sigma) = \exp\{-(\sigma/\sigma_0)^w\} \quad (2)$$

The parameter $\ln.\ln[1/S_L]$ is plotted vs. $\ln[\sigma]$ and fitted to a straight line of slope w and intercept σ_0 at $\ln.\ln[1/S_L] = 0$. This is known as a Weibull plot of the *first type*. If the assumption of a distribution of self similar flaws is correct, we would expect the parameter w to be the same for each set but σ_0 to vary according to the weak-link scaling equation:

$$\sigma_0 = \alpha L^{-1/w} \quad (3)$$

where α is the characteristic stress of the fibre at unit length [1 mm]. This should allow the characteristic stress for any gauge length to be estimated from data collected at different gauge length. This is very important in the analysis of the strength of composites since the *effective segment length* of a fibre embedded in a matrix is much smaller than the lengths which can be tested experimentally [eg 10 - 100 μm]. An alternative analysis is based on a plot of $\ln(\text{mean strength})$ vs. $\ln(\text{gauge length})$, a Weibull plot of the *second type*. According to the Weibull model this should be linear with a gradient of $(-1/w)$ allowing the weak-link estimation to be made directly from the plot. Unfortunately when experimental data are analyzed by both of these techniques the estimates of w from the *second type* of plot often differ significantly from those from plots of the *first type*. The reasons for this discrepancy must lie either in the original assumptions or be due to experimental problems.

A number of potential sources of experimental error may be identified by consideration of the nature of the fibres, sampling procedures and test methods. If we consider PAN-based carbon fibres: They are typically of 5 - 8 μm diameter with Young's modulus in the range 200 - 350 GPa and strengths ranging from 1 - 5 GPa. The fibres are manufactured from tows of 6000 or 12000 PAN filaments and converted to carbon (graphite) by a two or three thermo-, chemical-, mechanical treatments. They are then usually surface treated and often sized with a thin coating of resin. We might, therefore, expect the fibres to contain flaws originating from impurities or imperfections in the

precursor and from abrasion during the processing cycle. It is also likely that there will be fibre-to-fibre variations within the tow. It is observed that there are considerable differences in fibre diameter within a single length of tow. This, perhaps, originates from diameter variations in the precursor fibre due to differences in the hole sizes in the spinnerets, and possibly from differences in the degree of chemical conversion between fibres which lie on the outside of the tow, and are thus more exposed to the oxidising atmosphere in the first stage of conversion than fibres in the middle of the tow. It has been shown [1] that the smaller diameter fibres tend to be stronger. It is also likely that the degree of abrasion damage will vary from fibre-to-fibre within the tow. These factors will increase the intrinsic strength variability and also increase the possibility of sampling errors.

A single tow may contain 12000 individual fibres. When making strength measurements a number of fibres are selected from a short length of tow. Typically, 20 - 100 tests are made at each gauge length, so that even if tests are made at, say, 4 different gauge lengths the total sample might be less than 3% of the fibres in a short [100 mm] length of the tow. For example, Priest [2] made approximately 300 tests on fibres taken from a 100 mm length of a 1000 filament tow.

Carbon fibres are of small diameter and have to be extracted from the tow, which is always twisted and tangled to some extent. This is quite tricky and many fibres will be lost or broken during the course of a test campaign. The fibres must then be stuck onto the test cards, their diameters measured and finally they must be placed in the testing apparatus and the cards cut away, before the test can proceed. At each stage fibres will be lost or broken so that the final data set represents only those fibres which survive the selection and test preparation procedure. It is probable that a greater proportion of the weaker fibres is lost in this way. In the case of carbon fibres we have found that "losses" are unacceptably high at gauge lengths greater than 100 mm and less than 10 mm.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

It is common practice when testing fibres to select a fibre from the tow and arbitrarily allocate the test gauge length. The likelihood is that every test in the set is on a different fibre. Now, we believe that the fibre-to-fibre variability is likely to be greater than the variability of strength **along** an individual fibre. We have established that the diameter does not vary significantly along fibre lengths of the order of 100 mm, whereas there are big differences between fibres and strength is inversely related to the diameter. A procedure has, therefore, been devised where tests are carried out on adjacent portions of a single fibre at 4 different gauge lengths.

The key to this procedure is a 4-aperture window card [fig 1]. This card contains apertures of 75, 30, 12 and 5 mm length arranged in series. [The lengths of the apertures were selected to fall at approximately equal intervals on a $\ln[\text{length}]$ plot. A 300 mm (approximately) length of fibre is selected from the tow and then positioned along the axis of the card. It is stuck to

the card with a quick setting cyano-acrylate adhesive applied at the points indicated a in the figure. The card is then cut, where indicated by the dotted lines, into 4 separate test cards with gauge lengths of 75, 30, 12 and 5 mm respectively. The fibre diameter is then measured, either by optical microscopy using a Watson Image Shearing Eyepiece [WISE] or by a laser diffraction method. Finally each card is mounted in the test machine, the side pieces cut with a hot wire and the tensile test performed. We then have a set of data comprising 4 strengths at the different gauge lengths for each fibre selected. The 4 lengths tested should differ only in their length but will, of course, still be subject to inadvertent damage during handling and testing. The non-parametric analysis described is based on this premise.

3. RESULTS

The total number of observations was 137, 139, 132 and 133, for lengths 5, 12, 30, and 75mm respectively, with complete data obtained for 121 fibres. The design of the experiment ensured that the distribution of diameter was virtually the same for each length, so it was natural to test initially whether the stress distributions conformed to a single Weibull distribution. Maximum likelihood estimates of w and α , and Weibull probability plots are shown in Table 1 and Figure 2. Clearly a single underlying distribution does not apply. A likelihood ratio test conducted as in Watson and Smith [3] indicates an overwhelming rejection of the hypothesis of a common Weibull strength distribution.

TABLE 1
MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD ESTIMATES OF WEIBULL PARAMETERS : CARBON FIBRES IN AIR

length(mm)	#obs	\hat{w}	s.e. (\hat{w})	$\hat{\alpha}$ (GPa)	s.e. ($\hat{\alpha}$)
5	137	6.09	0.2883	5.65	0.1955
12	139	4.37	0.1534	6.28	0.2548
30	132	7.45	0.2012	4.00	0.1276
75	133	9.47	0.2002	3.51	0.0990

(s.e. = standard error)

To see whether any of the lengths individually had a strength distribution acceptably close to Weibull, goodness-of-fit tests due to Cramer & Von-Mises and Anderson & Darling were applied, suitably modified to take account of parameter estimation. Stephens [4] has made specific calculations for how the above tests should be conducted in the case of the extreme value, or Gumbel distribution, which may be used here, since if the variable X has a Weibull distribution, then $Z = \log X$ has a Gumbel distribution. Table 2 shows the computed W^2 and A^2 statistics. All reject the Weibull model at the 1% level of significance, the departure being particularly extreme for the 12 and 30 mm lengths.

TABLE 2
GOODNESS-OF-FIT STATISTICS

	5mm	12mm	30mm	75mm	99%tile
Cramer-Von-Mises \bar{W}^2	0.1947	0.3273	0.6403	0.2129	0.175
Anderson-Darling A^2	1.6277	2.2941	3.4606	1.182	1.038

It is worth noting that the popular plot of $\ln(\text{mean strength})$ against $\ln(\text{gauge length})$ [Figure 3], giving $w = 4.02$, is a poor indicator of the extent of departure from a common underlying Weibull distribution.

Departure from the Weibull model is not, however, a test of departure from weakest-link. This latter property is a fundamental one and must be considered in the process of explaining departure and suggesting alternative failure models. Here a simple test of the weakest-link principle is described, based on strength measurements from different lengths of the same fibre, but requiring no knowledge of the strength distribution.

4. A NON-PARAMETRIC TEST

Suppose a homogeneous fibre of length L is partitioned into lengths $L_1, L_2, L_3, \dots, L_n$, where $L_n < L_{n-1} < \dots < L_2 < L_1$, and the failure stresses of each length noted and ranked, $1, 2, \dots, n$ in increasing order. There are $n!$ ways in which these rankings could occur, and the probability of each ordering depends on assumptions made about the underlying chance mechanism. Under the weakest-link hypothesis, at any point in the loading process every unit length element has an equal chance, say p_0 , of failing next, regardless of where the element may be situated within the length of fibre.

Take the case $n = 4$, and let l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4 be the lengths of the sections failing 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th respectively. The probability of length l_1 failing first is l_1/L . There is then a total length $L - l_1$ left, and the probability that length l_2 is next to fail is $l_2/(L - l_1)$, and so on.

So,

$$P(\text{order is } l_1, l_2, l_3, l_4) = \frac{l_1}{L} \frac{l_2}{(L - l_1 - l_2)} \quad (4)$$

Similarly the probabilities for all possible orderings may be calculated. The null hypothesis dictates that fibres are on average weaker than fibres which are shorter, i.e. the probability of encountering a fatal flaw is higher. It is to be expected therefore that the most likely order of failure is L_1, L_2, L_3, L_4 . A test of the weakest-link hypothesis may then be based on comparison of expected frequencies under the multinomial model defined above with the observed frequencies of the various orders of failure, using a goodness-of-fit test such as Pearson's:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(x_i - np_i)^2}{np_i}, \quad (5)$$

where x_i and np_i are respectively the observed and expected frequencies for the i th order of failure (cell). It is customary to group cells where the expected frequencies fall below some minimum level, e_{\min} , say. An oft quoted value for e_{\min} is 5, though it is recognised that this tends to be conservative, dependent on the significance level and the number of cells. With a highly skew multinomial and a large number of cells this inevitably results in a high degree of grouping. For categorical data there is often no natural way to group cells as there is with ordinal or quantitative data. To help maximise the number of cells for a given e_{\min} the failure orders are sorted into descending probability of occurrence and then "neighbouring" cells grouped appropriately. The value yielded for X^2 is compared with an appropriate percentage point of X^2 using $k - 1$ degrees of freedom, where k is the number of cells after grouping. The application of the non-parametric test to the above data is shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3
NON-PARAMETRIC TEST : CARBON FIBRES IN AIR

Event	Probability	Expected frequency (np_i)	Observed frequency (x_i)
1 2 3 4	0.2770	33.52	99
2 1 3 4	0.1415	17.12	9
1 3 2 4	0.1345	16.27	3
1 2 4 3	0.1154	13.96	7
2 1 4 3	0.0589	7.13	0
3 1 2 4	0.0575	6.96	2
1 4 2 3	0.0467	5.65	0
2 3 1 4	0.0301	6.68	1
3 2 1 4	0.0251		
1 3 4 2	0.0224	4.98	0
4 1 2 3	0.0188		
<i>the rest</i>	0.0721	8.73	0

('1' = 75mm, '2' = 30mm, '3' = 12mm, '4' = 5mm)

This yields $X^2 = 178.6$ which exceeds by an enormous margin the 99% of the $X^2_{(9)}$ distribution, which is 21.67. By far the largest contribution to X^2 was due to the most likely order of failure (1 2 3 4), with probability 0.277, occurring over 80% of the time. Adjacent pairs of lengths were also examined individually to see whether the weakest-link principle broke down at any particular point, but all pairs showed a similar degree of departure. Therefore the evidence is overwhelming that for these fibres at these lengths the weakest-link principle does not apply. In particular, if a certain length fails at stress σ , it is very unlikely that the next shorter length will fail at stress less than σ . This has considerable implications not only with regard to the form of the model chosen for stress distribution, but also to the important question of strength prediction.

5. FURTHER DISCUSSION

It is usually hard to accept on physical grounds that dependence of flaws is a possible reason for the breakdown of weakest-link. It is plausible that the assumption of only one essential type of flaw is unrealistic, but the presence of multiple flaw types will only make a difference in the test if it results in the probability of unit element failure, p_0 , being dependent on section length.

As an illustration, suppose that at any given stress, unit elements have an unequal probability of failing next, dependent on section length. The experiments cited here have been designed so that adjacent lengths are in approximately the same ratio. i.e. $L_1 : L_2$, $L_2 : L_3$, and $L_3 : L_4$ are all about 1 : 2.5. Let a constant scaling of length enhance the probability of unit element failure by a factor of c , so that these probabilities are in the ratio $c^3 : c^2 : c : 1$, for lengths L_1, L_2, L_3, L_4 respectively; c greater than 1 makes a shorter length stronger than predicted under weakest-link. For these experiments, the probability of the 1, 2, 3, 4 ordering becomes:

$$\frac{75 c^3 30 c^2 12 c}{(75c^3 + 30c^2 + 12c + 5) (30c^2 + 12c + 5) (12c + 5)} \quad (6)$$

For this to yield an expected number of such ordering in line with the number of times observed in Table 3, c would have to be approximately 6.

The presence of multiple modes of failure has been recognised and observed by a number of workers, including Clarke [5], and Henstenburg and Phoenix [6]. Frequently a competing risks model has been suggested, the overall survivor function being the product of the independent survivor functions for each mode type.

However, if it is still assumed that each failure type has Weibull-distributed strength, and therefore obeys the weakest-link relation, then the overall distribution will also comply with weakest-link.

i.e. if

$$S_L^{(i)}(\sigma) = \{S_1^{(i)}(\sigma)\}^L \text{ and } S_L(\sigma) = \prod_{i=1}^k S_L^{(i)}(\sigma), \quad (7)$$

then

$$S_L(\sigma) = \prod_{i=1}^k \{S_1^{(i)}(\sigma)\}^L = \left\{ \prod_{i=1}^k S_1^{(i)}(\sigma) \right\}^L, \quad (8)$$

which satisfies relation (1).

There are various other alternatives based on the Weibull distribution, but a number still conform to the weakest-link theory. If the non-parametric weakest-link test proves significant, then all of these possibilities may be rejected.

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FIGURE 1. The 4-window test card used for mounting the single-fibre test specimens. The card is cut to form the 4 test specimens of different gauge length.

FIGURE 2. Weibull plots for the four carbon-fibre data sets. Note the pronounced bi-modality of the 12 mm data.

FIGURE 3. A plot of $\ln[\text{mean strength}]$ vs $\ln[\text{length}]$ which illustrates the weak link scaling principle.

